

Appendix: Methodological toolbox

Tool no. 3_4_2_1	
Title	Citizen Science (CS) initiatives.
Category	Environmental/Socio-cultural.
Purpose of the method	Citizen science initiatives aim to engage the public in environmental research, focusing on monitoring biodiversity, pollution, climate change impacts, etc.. The ability to foster engagement is as important as the ability to gain useful monitoring habitat or biodiversity monitoring information. The scientific value of the data collected through citizen science can be improved through careful planning at the outset to collect data that accounts for covariates and to address issues of coverage and spatial bias. Training of citizen scientists at the outset of data collection is key. Statistical techniques can help to address issues of observer variation and spatial bias and benchmarking citizen science datasets with those collected by professional surveyors will help to address issues of identification errors.
Effort in time	Usually, the time required for CS initiatives is defined depending on the research/data collection method.
Number of objects investigated	Usually, the minimum number of investigated objects is defined depending on the research/CS initiative.
Data format	Qualitative, quantitative, spatial, temporal, images, and textual data.
Description	Citizen Science refers to the scientific work undertaken by members of the general public, in collaboration with or under the direction of professional scientists and scientific institutions. At the same time, a Citizen Scientist refers to a member of the general public who engages in scientific work, in collaboration with or under the direction of professional scientists and scientific institutions. Data is obtained from Citizen Science through standardised questionnaires and in-person interviews with the stakeholders involved in the initiatives. Data is analysed through tabulation (e.g., in Microsoft Excel [®]). Qualitative, quantitative and temporal tabulated data are processed with statistical software (e.g., R for statistics). When spatial information is available, data is processed in Geo-spatial Information System (GIS) environments.
Basic Literature	<i>Backstrom, L. J., Callaghan, C. T., Leseberg, N. P., Sanderson, C., Fuller, R. A., & Watson, J. E. M. (2024). Assessing adequacy of citizen science datasets for biodiversity monitoring. Ecology and Evolution, 14, e10857. https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.10857</i> <i>Barańczuk, K., & Barańczuk, J. (2021). Smart control of the climate resilience of European Coastal City (SCORE) HORIZON 2020-Coastal City Living Lab-Case of Gdańsk. Doctoral School of Natural Sciences. https://doi.org/10.3030/101003534</i>

	<p><i>Binley, A. D., & Bennett, J. R. (2023). The data double standard. Methods in Ecology and Evolution, 14, 1389–1397. https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.14110</i></p> <p><i>Bio Innovation Service, Directorate-General for Environment (European Commission), Fundación Ibercivis and The Natural History Museum (2018). Citizen science for environmental policy: Development of an EU-wide inventory and analysis of selected practices. Final report for the Directorate-General for Environment (European Commission), EU Publications https://doi.org/10.2779/961304</i></p> <p><i>Fraisl, D., Hager, G., Bedessem, B., et al. (2022). Citizen science in environmental and ecological sciences. Nature Reviews Methods Primers, 2, 64. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-022-00677-9</i></p> <p><i>Harley, M. D., & Kinsela, M. A. (2022). CoastSnap: A global citizen science program to monitor changing coastlines. Continental Shelf Research, 245, 104796. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csr.2022.104796</i></p> <p><i>Marrocco, V., Zangaro, F., Sicuro, A., & Pinna, M. (2019). A scaling down mapping of <i>Pinna nobilis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) through the combination of scientific literature, NATURA 2000, grey literature and citizen science data. Nature Conservation, 33, 21-31. https://doi.org/10.3897/natureconservation.33.30397</i></p>
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Linked material	<p>https://doi.org/10.3897/natureconservation.33.30397</p> <p>https://www.doccity.com/en/docs/capturing-our-coast-communications-and-key-messaging-to/8921881/</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csr.2022.104796</p>